

Annotation: In works related to the grammar of the Uzbek language, proper nouns are names, surnames, nicknames; geographical names; names of various organizations, enterprises, institutions, planets and stars; names of historical events, newspapers, magazines and scientific institutions; classified according to special names given to animals.

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If we analyze the number of nouns used in scientific and artistic speech from a quantitative point of view, it is known that, firstly, nouns are used more often in scientific speech than in artistic speech, and secondly, they are repeated a lot. There is an objective reason for this, of course. First, the scientific work studies the laws of things and events. Words naming things and events are directly related to nouns. secondly, each science studies its object through terms that represent a certain concept. The unambiguous character of the term ensures its frequent repetition.

It is noteworthy that there are peculiarities in the use of nouns in the scientific style. Therefore, before moving on to the peculiarities of noun forms in the scientific style, it is necessary to briefly dwell on the use of nouns in this style.

In works related to the grammar of the Uzbek language, proper nouns are the names, surnames, nicknames of people; geographical names; names of various organizations, enterprises, institutions, planets and stars; names of historical events, newspapers, magazines and scientific institutions; classified according to special names given to animals. Our investigations show that in scientific speech only nicknames of people and names given to animals do not occur in scientific speech. However, the other types of nouns mentioned above have their own characteristics in the use of scientific speech, or rather, in every science. In the speech of some subjects, proper nouns are used a lot, while in others they are used very little. The most common use of nouns is found in history and geography. For example, in the science of history, the term of rebellions, dynasties, empires associated with names of places, rivers, states, names of chiefs, names of people is often found: Central Asia, Movarunnahr, Kazakhstan, Shosh (Tashkent), Aloy Range Mountains, Caucasus, Middle East, Ghishtsoi, Karaboysoi, Khorazm State, Muqanna Uprising, Uprising under Abu Muslim, Samanid Dynasty, Kushan Empire, Karakhanids the reign of the Baburi dynasty, etc.

In geography, the names of continents, countries, oceans, seas, rivers, arms, mountains, oasis, lowlands are often used. Geography studies the topography, minerals, climatic features, underground water, soil, plants, and fauna of the places associated with the name. Therefore, it is natural to use many related nouns.

In the sciences of physics and mathematics, the names of laws, theorems, and discoveries related to people's names are often used.

Names and surnames of scientists are often found among famous nouns in every scientific language. In scientific discourse, the names and surnames of scientists of different nationalities are mentioned a lot. There are few Uzbek names and surnames. Names and patronymics used in scientific speech are abbreviated, first initials are given, and then the

surname is written in full. In the literary speech, in the works of Uzbek writers, there are more Uzbek names and surnames, and fewer names and surnames of people of other nationalities. In artistic speech, the name and surname are not given in full, as in scientific speech.

In scientific speech, only the name itself is not used, and in this type of speech, the abbreviation of personal names is not used Muqat instead of Muqaddas, Mirsal instead of Mirsalim. Words denoting the names of relatives such as father, brother, uncle, sister do not come together with names and surnames: Akbar aka, Karim toga, Rasulov uncle. Nicknames given to people are not used in scientific speech: Anvar is resourceful, Juman is shy, Soli is cold, Ali is lazy, Chotir, Navnov, etc. Such famous nouns can be used in artistic speech. But scientific speech does not accept such famous nouns.

From the analysis of related nouns, it became clear that in this type of functional style abstract nouns are used more often than concrete nouns. The reason for this is that scientific speech itself is based on abstract thinking.

One of the characteristic features of concrete nouns used in scientific speech is their acquisition of a scientific concept. For example, from a scientific point of view, the words mountain, stone, and lung are understood in the sense of concrete objectivity in the sense of the reason for the formation of the mountain, its chemical composition, and the function of the lungs.

Another of its characteristic features is that concrete nouns are not used in subjective evaluation forms.

Abstract nouns refer to abstract signs, properties, concepts. They cannot be perceived through the senses. Abstract nouns used in scientific speech are characterized by a sign characteristic of this type of speech. For example, doctrine, rule, problem, system, category, character, feature, task, theorem, equation, method, type, etc. words like are abstract words that are typical for scientific speech.

In works on the grammar of the Uzbek language, it is said that abstract nouns do not take the suffix -al, and examples are love, flow. Words such as emotion, goodness, and beauty are mentioned. If the affix -lar is added, it is said that not plural, but additional meaning is expressed: feelings-feelings.

Almost all abstract nouns characteristic of scientific speech take the form -s: theorems, rules, categories, problems, categories, tasks, etc.

In scientific speech, abstract nouns used in the plural form do not serve to mean additional ottenka. They retain the true plural meaning when they take the affix -s: Grammar shows the opposition (contradiction) of two or more categorical forms to each other, the ways of formation of certain distributional groups of words and forms. , is a science that studies the methods of formation of transformational variants of each formal and constructional grammatical unit, etc.

Scientific speech is also unique in terms of the use of singular and collective nouns. Singular noun refers to one of the same type of noun. Singular nouns can be singular or plural: like people. The semantics of nouns is complex, and when they are used in the singular form, they can mean a single object or all of these objects in logical plural. For example, a book can be a specific book in question or any book in general. From this point of view, when the use of singular nouns is considered in scientific speech, it is known that singular nouns are used mainly

in the sense of logical plural. Such use of nouns in scientific speech is one of its typical signs, and concrete, single nouns have a logical plural and collective meaning.

Scientific speech has its own characteristics not only in terms of the meaning of the word, but also in terms of the use of forms specific to the noun group. Such uniqueness is especially visible in the use of plural and possessive forms. In the use of other forms, we did not find signs that are characteristic only for the scientific style.

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